

DAMAGE TOLERANT TOW-BASED DISCONTINUOUS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Tow-based discontinuous composites combine the high-performance of carbon-fibres with the manufacturability of short-fibre composites, but their unique multiscale microstructure results in a very complex mechanical response yet to be fully understood. This work analyses the tensile response of several tow-based discontinuous composites with different matrices and microstructures, focusing on the failure and toughening mechanisms of the materials. It is shown that the fracture toughness of tow-based discontinuous composites is remarkably high (reaching 100 kJ/m²), which contributes to their notch-insensitive response. These materials are therefore suitable for structural applications, particularly when defect/damage tolerance and energy absorption are required.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-Fibre Reinforced-Polymers (CFRPs) offer exceptionally high specific stiffness and strength, and are now the preferred material for structural applications requiring high performance and lightweight. However, conventional CFRPs – based on a structured and continuous fibre architecture – usually require very costly and time-consuming manufacturing processes (such as manual lay-up and autoclave curing), which makes these materials unsuitable for large-volume industries (such as automotive). Short-fibre composites circumvent these problems, but at the expense of a much lower performance due to a typically reduced fibre-content.

Multiscale carbon-fibre discontinuous composites (MCFDCs) are a new family of high-performance discontinuous composites combining the manufacturability of short-fibre composites with the high performance of carbon-fibres. These materials are characterised by a two-levels reinforcement architecture: at the mesoscale, the material is reinforced by randomly-oriented discontinuous bundles (25-50 mm long), with each bundle being composed of thousands of aligned fibres at the microscale; this architecture allows for high fibre-contents, while keeping the material mouldable. MCFDCs can be produced from chopped prepreg (e.g. HexMC [1] by Hexcel), spray deposition and resin infusion [2], or tow-based advanced SMC (e.g. Forged Composites [3] by Quantum Composites).

Existing literature on MCFDCs shows that these materials can match the conventional quasi-isotropic continuous counterparts in terms of stiffness [4], and are also notch-insensitive [5, 6]. However, most research has focused so far on characterising lab-based materials, and there is virtually no in-depth understanding on the failure mechanisms and damage tolerance of commercially-available materials.

This work analyses the response of several commercially-available tow-based discontinuous composites (manufactured through advanced SMC), aiming to characterise the effect of different fibre-architectures and matrices on mechanical properties, and to further investigate the damage tolerance of these materials by, for the first time in the literature, measuring their fracture toughness.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

Five tow-based discontinuous materials – with different matrices and different filament counts – were analysed in this work, as described in Table 1. All materials are commercially available from Quantum Composites [7-11], and present a high content of carbon fibres (above 45% in volume) and 25.4 mm (1-in) long tows.

Table 2 describes the mechanical tests performed with the tow-based discontinuous composites. Since all materials were nominally isotropic in-plane, all tests were performed along one direction only. All strains and displacements were measured using an optical extensometer.

Unnotched tensile tests [12] were used to measure the Young’s modulus (calculated from a linear-regression of the stress-strain curve in the range of 0.05-0.15% strains) and the unnotched tensile strength of the materials. The flaw tolerance of the composites was investigated through open-hole tensile tests [13], considering four values of width-to-diameter ratio (between 3.125 and 12.5).

The in-plane fracture toughness of the materials was measured through Compact Tension (CT) tests [14], using Finite-Element Analysis (FEA)-based compliance calibration for the data reduction. This implied using the experimental compliance (calculated by tracking the opening-displacement at the base of the notch) to evaluate the values of crack length and energy release rate throughout each test, based on linear-elastic FEA run at several different crack lengths. The tensile fracture surfaces of the CT specimens were analysed using optical and scanning-electron microscopy.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Unnotched tensile tests

Figure 1 presents the results of the unnotched tensile tests for the discontinuous composites analysed. Both stiffness and strength are lower for the 12k-tow materials, which also present a larger variability (Figure 1a) and more non-linear stress-strain curves (Figure 1b). The results for the 3k-tow materials suggest that the type of matrix influences the ultimate tensile strength, but has no significant effect on the Young’s modulus. The stiffness of the EP-12k material appears to be uncharacteristically low; this was likely due to a degree of preferential orientation along the transverse direction of the specimens, which would also contribute to the low strength measured for this material.

Table 1: Description of tow-based discontinuous materials studied.

Material reference	Matrix	Tow count	Fibre weight fraction (%)
EP-3k	Epoxy (EP)	3,000 (3k)	55
VE-3k	Vinyl ester (VE)	3,000 (3k)	50
BMI-3k	Bismaleimide (BMI)	3,000 (3k)	53
EP-12k	Epoxy (EP)	12,000 (12k)	55
VE-12k	Vinyl ester (VE)	12,000 (12k)	50

Table 2: Description of the mechanical tests performed.

Test type	Standard / reference	Displacement rate (mm/min)	Nominal thickness (mm)	Specifications
Unnotched tension	ASTM D3039 [12]	1.0	3	Specimen width: 25 mm
Open-hole tension	ASTM D5766 [13]	1.0	3	Specimen width: 25 mm Hole diameters: 2, 4, 6, 8 mm
Compact tension	Pinho et al., 2006 [14]	1.0	5	

a) Average strength vs. stiffness. b) Representative stress-strain curve for each material.

Figure 1: Results from the unnotched tensile tests of tow-based discontinuous composites.

3.2 Open-hole tensile tests

Figure 2a shows that, for the 3k materials with epoxy and VE matrices, the gross strength (calculated based on the unnotched cross-section) is not reduced by the presence of small circular notches (with diameter of 2-4 mm); for larger notches, the gross strength is progressively reduced. The BMI-3k and both 12k-tow materials appear to be even more insensitive to the presence of holes, with stable gross strength up to a 6 mm diameter. This is corroborated by Figure 2b, which shows that most specimens with 2 mm notches actually fail away from the machined holes, with the 12k-tow materials showing a slower increase of the frequency of net failure with increasing hole diameter.

3.3 Compact tension tests

Figure 3 presents the first measurements in the literature of the in-plane fracture toughness of tow-based discontinuous composites. All materials exhibit outstanding values of fracture toughness (Figure 3a), overcoming 100 kJ/m² for the VE-12k composite. Materials with 12k-tows present higher fracture toughness than those with 3k-tows, although with a less stable crack growth (see Figure 3b); composites with a VE or BMI matrix also lead to higher fracture toughnesses than with epoxy. All materials present a raising R-curve up to a 5-10 mm long process zone.

a) Gross strength vs. hole diameter. b) Percentage of failures at the hole.

Figure 2: Results from the open-hole tensile tests of tow-based discontinuous composites.

a) Average maximum fracture toughness.

b) Representative R-curve for each material.

Figure 3: Results from the compact tension tests of tow-based discontinuous composites.

3.4 Fractography

A representative CT fracture surface of each material analysed is shown in Figure 4. This reveals both tow fracture and tow pull-out as the main failure mechanisms; the former prevails in 3k-tow materials with epoxy or VE matrix, while the latter dominates in the BMI and 12k-tow materials. Figure 5 suggests that the interfacial adhesion of the carbon-fibres with the VE matrix is considerably better than with the BMI matrix.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Effect of the matrix and microstructure on mechanical properties

From the three types of matrix included in this study (epoxy, vinylester and bismaleimide), the VE-materials show the best performance in terms of strength (Figures 1 and 2) and fracture toughness (Figure 3); since this matrix also has the shortest curing cycle (5-10 min), it appears to be optimal for tow-based discontinuous composites. This work also demonstrates that using a BMI matrix leads to a considerably lower composite strength than when using EP or VE matrices (Figures 1 and 2), most likely due to poor infusion and/or reduced fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Fracture surfaces of tow-based discontinuous composites.

a) Evidence of good adhesion with VE matrix. b) Evidence of poor adhesion with BMI matrix.

Figure 5: Scanning electron microscope image of the surface of pulled-out tows.

Modifying the filament count of the tows in the composite (3k vs. 12k) has a strong influence on the failure and toughening mechanisms of the materials. Using lower filament counts leads to a higher stiffness and strength (Figure 1), as tensile stresses are more efficiently transferred between bundles. However, composites with heavier tows (12k) exhibit a higher fracture toughness due to the increasing amount of energy dissipated through friction during pull-out (Figure 3 and 4). This is in agreement with existing literature on virgin and recycled discontinuous composites [15, 16].

4.2 Defect and damage tolerance

The results obtained with the notched specimens show that tow-based discontinuous materials are very tolerant to defects and damage. The extremely high values of fracture toughness measured (Figure 3) are a direct result of the unstructured and discontinuous architecture of the reinforcement, which leads to energy dissipation through debonding and pull-out – both at the individual-fibre and tow levels – and to the formation of very large damage process zones (Figures 4 and 5).

The notch-insensitive behaviour of tow-based discontinuous composites shown in Figure 2 has also been observed in the literature for prepreg-based materials [5, 6], whereby it was attributed to the presence of inherent stress-concentrations and defects in the microstructure of the material. However, the results from the CT tests (Figure 3) suggest that the notch-insensitivity observed in Figure 2 can also be (at least partially) due to the very high values of fracture toughness measured. This is further corroborated by the fact that the materials with the highest fracture toughness (i.e. with 12k tows) also withstood the highest loads in the CT tests and were the least affected by large circular holes, despite having the lowest unnotched tensile strength.

4.3 Potential for structural applications

Figure 6 shows that tow-based discontinuous composites present competitive values of specific stiffness and specific fracture toughness, when compared to conventional lightweight materials.

As opposed to prepreg-based discontinuous composites tested in the literature [4], the family of SMC-based discontinuous composites analysed in this work does not reach the stiffness of conventional quasi-isotropic CFRP, due to the lower fibre-content in the former (between 45-50% in volume, compared to 60% in prepreg-based composites). Nevertheless, the materials analysed in this study present values of specific stiffness similar to those of aerospace-graded aluminium and titanium, and much higher values of fracture toughness.

Figure 6: Specific fracture toughness vs. specific stiffness of tow-based discontinuous composites and other conventional lightweight materials (aluminium 2024-T4 [17], titanium grade 5 [18], and cross-ply CFRP [14]).

The high values of fracture toughness measured in this study in tow-based discontinuous composites demonstrate that these materials are particularly suitable to applications requiring not only high stiffness, but also high damage/defect tolerance and energy absorption. Moreover, the strength of discontinuous composites is much less sensitive to the presence of holes than conventional composites with continuous fibres, thus offering a great advantage for most real-life structural applications.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work analysed the tensile response of five commercially-available high-performance tow-based discontinuous composites, leading to the following conclusions:

- Vinylester matrices provide optimal manufacturability and performance (over epoxy and BMI);
- Lighter tows lead to higher stiffness and unnotched strength, while heavier tows lead to higher fracture toughness and defect/damage tolerance;
- The unnotched mechanical properties of tow-based discontinuous composites are similar to those of aluminium and titanium; moreover, the materials are insensitive to small notches and tougher than lightweight metals and conventional composites. This suggests that tow-based discontinuous composites are particularly well-suited for structural applications in which damage/defect tolerance and energy absorption are critical.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Hexcel Corporation, "HexMC User guide", 2014. Available online: http://www.hexcel.com/Resources/UserGuides/HexMC_User%20Guide.pdf (last accessed: May 2015).

- [2] L. T. Harper, T. A. Turner, *et al.*, "Characterisation of random carbon fibre composites from a directed fibre preforming process: The effect of tow filamentisation," *Compos Part a-Appl S*, **38**, pp.755-770, 2007.
- [3] P. Feraboli, F. Gasco, *et al.*, "Carbon fibre innovation for high volumes: the forged composite", 2011. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/papers/2011-ASC-montreal-forged-suspens.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [4] P. Feraboli, E. Peitso, *et al.*, "Characterization of Prepreg-Based Discontinuous Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Systems," *J Reinf Plast Comp*, **28**, pp.1191-1214, 2009.
- [5] P. Feraboli, E. Peitso, *et al.*, "Notched behavior of prepreg-based discontinuous carbon fiber/epoxy systems," *Compos Part a-Appl S*, **40**, pp.289-299, 2009.
- [6] C. Qian, L. T. Harper, *et al.*, "Notched behaviour of discontinuous carbon fibre composites: Comparison with quasi-isotropic non-crimp fabric," *Compos Part a-Appl S*, **42**, pp.293-302, 2011.
- [7] Quantum Composites, "Lytex 4149 Technical Data Sheet", 2013. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/datasheets/lytex/Quantum-Lytex-4149.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [8] Quantum Composites, "AMC 8593 Technical Data Sheet", 2013. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/datasheets/amc/Quantum-AMC-8593%20126-76-118.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [9] Quantum Composites, "HTC 9593 Technical Data Sheet", 2013. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/datasheets/hightemp/Quantum-HTC-9593%20127-51-5.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [10] Quantum Composites, "Lytex 4181 Technical Data Sheet", 2013. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/datasheets/lytex/Quantum-Lytex-4181.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [11] Quantum Composites, "AMC 8590 Technical Data Sheet", 2013. Available online: <http://www.quantumcomposites.com/pdf/datasheets/amc/Quantum-AMC-8590%20126-76-8.pdf> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [12] ASTM International, "D 3039/D 3039M Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials," ed. West Conshohocken, USA, 2008.
- [13] ASTM International, "D 5766/D 5766M Standard Test Method for Open-Hole Tensile Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates," ed. West Conshohocken, USA, 2008.
- [14] S. T. Pinho, P. Robinson, *et al.*, "Fracture toughness of the tensile and compressive fibre failure modes in laminated composites," *Compos Sci Technol*, **66**, pp.2069-2079, 2006.
- [15] S. Pimenta and S. T. Pinho, "An analytical model for the translaminar fracture toughness of fibre composites with stochastic quasi-fractal fracture surfaces," *J Mech Phys Solids*, **66**, pp.78-102, 2014.
- [16] S. Pimenta and S. T. Pinho, "The influence of micromechanical properties and reinforcement architecture on the mechanical response of recycled composites," *Compos Part a-Appl S*, **56**, pp.213-225, 2014.
- [17] ASM Inc., "Aluminum 2024-T4/2024-T351 material datasheet", 2001. Available online: <http://asm.matweb.com/search/SpecificMaterial.asp?bassnum=MA2024T4> (last accessed: May 2015).
- [18] ASM Inc., "Titanium Ti-6Al-4V (Grade 5), annealed material datasheet". Available online: <http://asm.matweb.com/search/SpecificMaterial.asp?bassnum=MTP641> (last accessed: May 2015).